

USE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Annotation: Distance education is a distance interaction of students and teachers with each other, and such distance education includes almost all components characteristic of the educational process (styles, goals, organizational forms, content and often teaching tools) and is carried out through special means of telecommunication technologies that ensure the interactivity of the educational process.

Introduction

It is known that in Article 16 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education, distance education is aimed at distance learning using information and communication technologies and the Internet.

A personal or laptop computer and a quality Internet connection are required for quality implementation of distance education. But for certain reasons, this is not always possible.

Accordingly, it is important to implement distance education with the help of mobile education (M-Learning).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Doskajanov Ch.T., Danenova U.N., Kokkoz M.M. The article “Rol mobilnyx prilozheniy v sisteme obrazovaniya” published in the 2nd issue of the international magazine “Experimental Education” in 2018 highlights the possibilities of using mobile applications in distance education.

In the literature, the thesis of the article entitled "Methods of using information technologies to increase the effectiveness of the teaching process" published in the

collection “Materials of scientific and creative conferences on mathematics, physics, computer science, chemistry and biology”, in which traditional and remote classes possibilities of using multimedia technologies are presented.

Also, the literature contains instructions and suggestions on “Using Internet resources during the lesson”.

In this scientific work, several proposals are presented on the organization of distance education based on mobile education. The effectiveness and disadvantages that may arise from their implementation are listed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Mobile learning is e-learning through mobile devices without the limitation of location or changes in student location.

Thus, mobile education, regardless of time and space, involves the use of mobile technology separately and together with other information and communication technologies to organize the distance learning process.

In the world of computers, the term mobile device refers to any electronic device that can be easily moved from one place to another. Over time, this category included mobile phones, laptops, smartphones, smart watches and other portable devices.

Today, a mobile device usually refers to any portable computer that runs applications that can connect to the Internet wirelessly. However, by today's more stringent standards, the category continues to expand with new inventions. As with any computing-related industry, our mobile devices continue to offer more advanced features while reducing size and weight.

Mobile devices include:

- mobile phones;
- smartphones;
- communicators (Personal Digital Assistant);
- portable radios;
- photo cameras;
- tablets;

- smart watches;
- music players;
- electronic books.

Mobile devices are united by the presence of an autonomous power source (accumulator or ordinary non-rechargeable batteries), small size and weight, control elements in the form of buttons, touch screens (touch screens), remote control via a radio channel (bluetooth, WiFi, etc.). Mobil qurulmalardan foydalanish quyidagi imkoniyatlarni yaratib beradi:

- providing new means of communication and cooperation allows to connect the study in the classroom with the study outside the classroom, with the study on the way home and with the study between classes;
- providing an opportunity for homeschoolers to share information, ask questions, and practice new skills;
- students become producers of knowledge: comments, discussions or exchange of electronic notes change the traditional role of the teacher as an undisputed authority to a more modern role of a partner or coach; the results of such discussions among students are an important pedagogical resource and ensure the transition to real education;
- recording and recording is facilitated in the work environment, which is seen as evidence of participation in learning or as a way to combine formal and informal learning.

A mobile application is a program installed on a specific platform that allows you to perform various actions.

The use of mobile applications for educational institutions allows:

- implementation of unified control over students' level of knowledge;
- simplification of testing and control works;
- acceleration of information exchange between all participants of the educational process, simplification of the process of interaction between teachers and students;

- activation and modernization of the educational process;
- organization of a distributed educational resource;
- ensuring the joint activity of students regardless of the location of the participants of the educational process;
- using a mobile device as a personal media library of educational, methodological and reference materials;
- connecting a mobile device to equipment and devices in the network of an educational institution for educational and scientific purposes;
- using mobile applications and embedded sensors to collect environmental data for educational and research purposes.

Let's get acquainted with some useful mobile applications.

MalMath is a powerful mathematical program created on Android for solving simple and more complex problems with a step-by-step description of each operation and a graphical representation of the given formulas.

Math Helper (Mathematics Assistant) is an Android application that is an indispensable utility for taking exams, sessions, writing homework, working with mathematics, algebra, geometry, matrices, systems of equations and systems of vectors.

GeoGebra is a great multi-functional cross-platform math application that supports Windows, iPhone, iPad, and Android, and is a good helper for anyone who needs to learn or perform various math operations in some way.

Maxima is a free computer algebra system for working with symbolic and numerical expressions under Windows OS control.

The main issues that can be solved using mobile devices:

- providing quick access to local networks and Internet educational and information resources;
- organization of interaction between teachers and students in real time;
- to provide the opportunity to learn without being tied to a certain place, in some cases, the time of classes during the presentation of the lecture material;

➤ to provide an opportunity to work using software in classrooms not equipped with computers.

Situations that cannot be solved using mobile devices:

- lack of technical tools with a set of necessary functions in some trainees;
- low methodological preparation of teachers to introduce mobile devices into the educational process;
- insufficient amount of ready mobile educational resources and programs for students in different areas of educational activity;
- mobile devices encourage students and schoolchildren to engage in entertainment activities (games, communication, viewing video and audio resources) during the educational process.
- small screen size and low permeability.

To date, only the last two cases can be classified as difficult to eliminate.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that organizing the educational process in educational institutions based on mobile applications creates a number of conveniences related to the rapid updating of educational materials based on the latest achievements of science.

Teaching education on the basis of mobile applications leads to greater individualization of education. As a result of this, as a result of the student's independent search for himself, the ability to work independently develops, and mastery indicators develop. The control work included in the mobile applications acquires practical importance as it monitors the student's learning process.

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